

A Study on the Complexation Equilibrium of Metal-EDTA from Viscometry

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A simple method to study complexation equilibria from viscosity measurement has been attempted. The reactions studied were those involving the use of EDTA. The method is based on the principle of additivity of the viscosity B -coefficients of the Jones-Dole's equation. A relative order of stability of the given metal-EDTA complexes has been inferred from the equilibrium relations so derived, and this order has been compared with the one derived from the corresponding stability constants.

It is well-established that the viscosity B -coefficients of the Jones-Dole's equation are additive in the sense that the B -coefficient differences between pairs of salts, having common anions, are constant in dilute solutions and independent of the nature of the anion^{1,2}. An attempt was made to extend such principle of additivity of the viscosity B -coefficient to a mixture of electrolyte solutions, each of which is characterised by a specific B value³. The specific cases examined by these authors were the dissociation equilibria in mixtures of weak acids and their salts. The present study proposes to test such extension of additivity principle to reaction system involving complexation equilibria. The systems studied have been those involving reaction equilibrium between bivalent metal sulphates and versene (disodium EDTA), which leads to the formation of metal-EDTA chelate complexes. The validity of such principle of extended additivity has been put to an experimental test for these reaction systems by way of deriving self-consistent expressions for the 'degree of reaction' (α)⁴ and equilibrium constant (K_o), and checking the same against the literature values of the corresponding thermodynamic stability constants of the given complexes.

Theory and working formulae: The equilibrium constant, or quotient (K_c) for the reaction,

is given by

$$K_c = \frac{(\text{M}^{\text{II}}\text{EDTA})_{\text{eq}} (\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4)_{\text{eq}}}{(\text{Na}_2\text{EDTA})_{\text{eq}} (\text{M}^{\text{II}}\text{SO}_4)_{\text{eq}}} \quad (2)$$

the assumptions being made that the activity coefficients are unity for the given dilute system.

Let an equimolar mixture of Na_2EDTA and the metal sulphate, $\text{M}^{\text{II}}\text{SO}_4$, at concentration C (mol dm^{-3}) of each, of which X (mol dm^{-3}) reacts at equilibrium forming the products, be considered. The various equilibrium concentrations are given by

$$(\text{M}^{\text{II}}\text{SO}_4)_{\text{eq}} = (C - X)$$

$$(\text{Na}_2\text{EDTA})_{\text{eq}} = (C - X)$$

$$(\text{M}^{\text{II}}\text{EDTA})_{\text{eq}} = X$$

$$(\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4)_{\text{eq}} = X$$

$$\text{So, } K_o = \frac{(X/C)^2}{(1-X/C)^2} = \frac{\alpha^2}{(1-\alpha)^2} \quad (3)$$

where $\alpha = X/C$, and may be termed the 'degree of reaction'⁴.

The equation of Jones and Dole⁵ proposed for describing the concentration-dependence of viscosity of electrolyte solutions is given as

$$\eta/\eta_o = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC \quad (4)$$

$$\text{or, } (\eta/\eta_o - 1)/\sqrt{C} = A + B\sqrt{C} \quad (5)$$

where η and η_o denote the respective coefficients of viscosity of a solution of molar concentration C and pure water at the same temperature, while A and B are empirical constants, sensitive to the solute-solute (Grüneisen effect) and solute-solvent interactions, respectively. B can be obtained graphically from viscosity studies on dilute solutions, i.e. from the slope of the best-fit linear plot of $(\eta/\eta_o - 1)/\sqrt{C}$ vs \sqrt{C} .

Let B_1 , B_2 , B_3 and B_4 be the viscosity B coefficients of pure Na_2EDTA , $\text{M}^{\text{II}}\text{SO}_4$, $\text{M}^{\text{II}}\text{EDTA}$ and Na_2SO_4 respectively, then the B -coefficient of an equimolar mixture of Na_2EDTA and $\text{M}^{\text{II}}\text{SO}_4$ (at concentration C mol dm^{-3} each), if there were no reaction, would be $C(B_1 + B_2)$ or CB^I . Then, if B^{II} be the observed B -coefficient of the equilibrium mixture of Na_2EDTA and $\text{M}^{\text{II}}\text{SO}_4$ (at concentration C mol dm^{-3} each), then assuming additivity of the viscosity B -coefficients at concentration C , one may write

$$B^{\text{II}}C = B^I(C - X) + XB_3 + XB_4$$

$$\text{or, } B^{\text{II}}C = B^IC - XB^I + XB_3 + XB_4$$

$$\text{or, } X(B^I - B_3 - B_4) = C(B^I - B^{\text{II}})$$

$$\text{or, } \frac{X}{C} = \alpha = \frac{(B^I - B^{II})}{(B_1^I - B_3 - B_4)} \quad (6)$$

On substituting α from equation (6) in equation (3) for K_0 , one obtains,

$$K_0 = \frac{\alpha^2}{(1-\alpha)^2} = \left(\frac{B^I - B^{II}}{B^I - B_3 - B_4} \right)^2 \left(1 - \frac{B^I - B^I}{B^I - B_3 - B_4} \right)^2 \quad (7)$$

The values of B_1 and B_2 (and hence, B^I), and B_4 were determined from independent experiments on solutions of Na_2EDTA , M^{II}SO_4 and Na_2SO_4 respectively, by using the Jones and Dole's equation (equation 5). A knowledge of B_3 and B^{II} is required to evaluate α and K_0 . B^{II} was obtained from observation on a single reaction mixture containing equimolar concentration (C molar) of Na_2EDTA and M^{II}SO_4 , i.e.

$$B^{II} = \left(\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} - 1 \right) / C \quad (8)$$

neglecting A -coefficient for such dilute solutions.

To determine B_3 , the following approximate method was used. To a large excess of M^{II}SO_4 (say, $0.2M$ when $C=0.2M$), a very small amount of Na_2EDTA (say, $0.02M$) was added and then assuming that the reaction (equation 1) was driven virtually completely to the right (with respect to Na_2EDTA) by the law of mass action, one would have the observed B -coefficient (say, B^{III}) of the mixture given as

$$\left(\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} - 1 \right) = C_{av} B^{III} = C_{av} (B_2 + B_3 + B_4) \quad (9)$$

where η is the observed viscosity coefficient of the mixture, B^{III} the 'composite' B -coefficient of the mixture (of 0.18 molar M^{II}SO_4 , 0.02 molar M^{II}EDTA , and 0.02 molar Na_2SO_4) and C_{av} the mean concentration of the mixture, and is given by

$$C_{av} = \frac{1}{3} (C_{\text{M}^{II}\text{SO}_4} + C_{\text{M}^{II}\text{EDTA}} + C_{\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4}) \quad (10)$$

Thus B_3 can be obtained with the aid of prior knowledge of B_2 and B_4 .

However, because of several approximations made in obtaining the different B terms and mean concentrations as described above, the emphasis in this study has been more on the qualitative order of stabilities of the present metal-EDTA complexes. An agreement between the latter and the order of stabilities as judged from the

corresponding stability constants, reported in the literature, is taken to indicate a satisfactory validation of the principle of extended additivity of the viscosity B -coefficient for the type of reaction mixtures investigated in the present study.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows B_1 for Na_2EDTA , B_2 for ZnSO_4 , MgSO_4 and MnSO_4 , and B_4 for Na_2SO_4 . It also shows the B^I values of ZnSO_4 , MgSO_4 and MnSO_4 and B^{II} values for equimolar mixtures at concentration $0.05 M$ of each of Na_2EDTA and different M^{II}SO_4 (such as MgSO_4 , ZnSO_4 and MnSO_4). The B_3 values of metal-EDTA and the calculated values of α , K_0 and pK_0 , obtained by substituting the values of B_1 , B_2 , B_3 , B_4 and B^{II} in equations (6) and (7), are also shown in Table 1.

On inspection of the pK_0 values (Table 1) it is evident that the stability of the metal-EDTA complexes, which is directly related to the corresponding K_0 values, falls in the order, $\text{ZnEDTA} > \text{MnEDTA} > \text{MgEDTA}$. This order is inversely related to the order of pK_0 values (Table 1). It is worthnoting that the stability constants (K) of these complexes also fall in the same order⁶ as K_0 (Table 1), and hence the findings of the present investigation are in qualitative agreement with those in the literature⁶ and obtained by independent techniques. The method described stability of a series of similar complexes by way of postulating an extension of the principle of additivity of viscosity B -coefficient for mixtures of the type investigated in the present case.

Experimental

A three-necked Ubbelohde all glass viscometer was used. The average flowtime for water (11 ml) through the capillary of the viscometer was 354.8 s at 35° . A thermostat with an accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ$ was used.

The chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The solutions were prepared in double-distilled water having conductance less than $3 \mu\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$.

The details of the experimental steps to obtain α and K_0 from viscosity measurements were as follows. (i) The B -coefficient (B_2) of zinc sulphate, magnesium sulphate, manganese(II) sulphate and sodium sulphate (B_4) were obtained

TABLE 1—SUMMARY OF B -COEFFICIENTS ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$), α , K_0 AND pK_0

Compd.	B_1^*	B_2^{**}	B_3	B_4^{***}	$B^I = B_1^* + B_2^{**}$	B^{II}^\dagger	B^{III}	α	K_0	pK_0	$\log K^\ddagger$
MgEDTA	0.90	0.55	-0.02	0.26	1.45	0.82	0.79	0.52	1.17	-0.07	8.70
ZnEDTA	0.90	0.42	0.43	0.26	1.32	0.76	1.11	0.89	65.4	-1.82	16.7
MnEDTA	0.90	0.62	0.19	0.26	1.52	0.85	1.07	0.62	2.66	-0.42	13.8

* B_1 value refers to Na_2EDTA . ** B_2 values refer to M^{II}SO_4 ($\text{M}^{II}=\text{Mg, Zn, Mn}$). *** B_4 value refers to Na_2SO_4 .

† B^{II} values refer to equimolar mixtures of Na_2EDTA and M^{II}SO_4 ($\text{M}^{II}=\text{Mg, Zn, Mn}$). ††Literature value (Ref. 6).

by noting the time of flow at different concentrations (0.05–0.2 *M*) of each of these solutions and water, all at 35°, and then having recourse to the graphical plot (viz. equation 5) in each case. (ii) B_1 for Na₂EDTA was similarly determined. (iii) B^{II} for an equimolar mixture of Na₂EDTA and M^{II}SO₄ (0.5*M* each) was obtained from observation on a single such mixture (viz. equation 8). (iv) To determine B_3 , the time of flow for a mixture of 0.2*M* M^{II}SO₄ and 0.02 *M* Na₂EDTA was noted, and the observed *B*-coefficient of the mixture (B^{III}) and hence B_3 of M^{II}EDTA were obtained by making use of equation (9). Here, $C_{av} = 1/3(0.180 + 0.02 + 0.02)M = 0.073M$ (viz. equation 10). (v) α and K_0 were then calculated

by substituting the values of B_1, B_3, B^I (i.e. $B_1 + B_2$), B_3, B_4 and B^{II} in equations (6) and (7).

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